

Revisiting The Colonial History of Chaiduar: Mass Mobilisation and Protest Movement Against The British Rule

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Abstract:

The people of Chaiduar, a historic place in the present Biswanath district of Assam, played an important role in the protest movements during India's struggle for freedom against the British colonial rule. The role played by martyrs like Kanaklata Baruah, Mukunda Kakati and the organizational activities led by the local leaders and workers of the Indian National Congress have been recorded in the history of Assam so far as freedom struggle is concerned. The success of this struggle during the entire course of the movement is credited to them and it is primarily considered their achievement. This is basically a traditional concept accepted by the historians who studied the history of the movement from above. In the last few decades, with the development of subaltern historiography, there is a drastic change in the process of history writing. Since the view that instead of the elite, people irrespective of class, caste and gender play vital role in the history making process became an established fact, the colonial history of Chaiduar and its contributions to India's struggle for freedom needs rethinking and revisit. Therefore, an attempt has been made in this paper to study the underlying factors behind the mobilisation of the common masses of Chaiduar and how different sections of people joined the protest movement against the colonial exploitation to overthrow the British rule.

The methodology to be followed in this study is historical and analytical. Attempt will be made to make the work objective so far as possible. Both primary and secondary sources will be used in the preparation of this work.

Keywords: Colonial Chaiduar, freedom movement, Kanaklata, Gohpur

Introduction:

The area, extending from the river Buroi up to Hawajan, in the eastern part of the erstwhile Darrang district and present Biswanath district, is known as Chaiduar since the Ahom period. During the British rule, this area was divided into four *Mouzas*, i.e. Kalangpur or Kalyanpur, Brahamjan,

Helem and Gohpur for administrative convenience.¹ A police station was also set-up at Gohpur in 1901 for the maintenance of law and order in that area.²

RISE OF NATIONAL AWARENESS IN CHAIDUAR:

National awareness came late to the people of Chaiduar. Prior to the Quit India Movement, there was no such major participation of the people from that area in the anti-British movement. Although, there were organized attempt to resist the British imperialist policy with some active men and women's participation. One such attempt was made in the form of Chaiduar Ryot Sabha held at Gamiri during the Civil Disobedience Movement. The president of this meeting was Chandraprba Saikiani³, the founder of the Assam Pradeshik Mahila Samiti, the first state level women organization of Assam. The meeting was also attended by Sri Sri Pitambardeva Goswami, Satradhikar of Garmur Satra, Majuli and Mukta-wala Vaishnavi, a Congress worker as chief guests. A large number of boys and girls, wearing white uniform and Gandhi-cap, took part in the procession.⁴ A cavalry of was organized with twelve girl volunteers under the initiative of Jyotiprasad Agarwala.⁵ This was a peculiar and perhaps the first instance to organized the people of that area.

The people of Chaiduar also inaugurated a new era in the history of film industry of Assam. A Few women of this area played roles in 'Joymoti' the first Assamese film, the shooting of which was also conducted at Bholaguri near Gohpur in 1934. Prominent among them were Bhaniti Burhagohain, Mohini Rajkumari and Brateswari Rajkumari. Ambika Barua of Balijan played the role of a child. Other actresses such as Aideu Handique, Makan Dutta and Phunu Baruah, who came from outside of that area, left a deep impression on people of Chaiduar.⁶ The involvement of lots of men and women in this film shooting roused a common sentiment against the British exploitation and inspired them to come forward together to participate in the protest movements.

WORLD WAR II AND ITS IMPACT ON THE POLITICS OF ASSAM:

World War II, which started in 1939, was a turning point in the history of modern India. Japan's victory in the initial phase of the war, failure of the Cripps Mission and declaration of war by the British Indian Government without the permission of the Congress created discontentment among the prominent leaders of India. Therefore on 8 August 1942 in the Bombay Session of the Congress. Mahatma Gandhi along with other leaders passed the 'Quit India' resolution and decided to launch a country wide agitation based on non-violence.⁷ Following the suggestion of All India Congress Committee (AICC), the Assam Provincial Congress Committee (APCC) started its preparation to launch the movement in the state. All the Congress volunteers of the state were organized into an efficient army known as *Santi Sena*. Almost 20,000 *Santi Senas* were prepared for this purpose. They were given regular training in the Congress camps. The members of the *Sena* kept themselves ready to meet any emergency arising out of the war situation.⁸

The APCC on the other hand decided to strengthen its volunteers' wings in the rural areas with a view to carry out the constructive works for maintenance of peace and order. Accordingly some sub-committees at the provincial, district and primary level were organized. The aim of these committees was to train *Santi Senas*. In erstwhile Darrang, the responsibility to form a district emergency sub-committee fell on the shoulders of Omio Kumar Das. As he was severely suffering from illness at that time, therefore the task of maintaining the Congress Movement in the district had to be carried out by his wife Pushpalata Das. Pushpalata along with Jyotiprasad Agarwala made a plan according to which the congress volunteers were divided into two corps, *Mrityu Bahini* or Death Squad and *Santi Bahini* or Peace Squad.⁹

ORGANIZATIONAL WORKS IN CHAIDUAR:

In Chaiduar some Congress units were established to organize the people of the villages. In addition to these units, training camps were also set up to train the members of *Mrityu Bahini* and *Santi Bahini*. The Kalabari congress Committee founded in 1937 was reorganised and undertook the task of training the Congress workers of that locality. In the same year another congress camp was also formed in Kalangpur *Mouza* under the Presidentship of Maghiram Bora. On 2 January 1942, a congress unit was started at Gohpur.¹⁰ Jogeswari Borah and Lakheswari Mahanta were actively associated with the Gohpur Congress Unit. Lakheswari Mahanta was entrusted with the Presidentship of the women unit. Her husband Golok Chandra Mahanta was also an active congress member of the Gohpur Unit. Their residence turned into a centre for regular meeting and discussions of the Congress workers. All the secret papers and documents of the Gohpur Congress Unit were hidden in the granary of their houses. A temporary office for this unit was set-up at Borigaon Tiniali near National Highway. The land for building the house was donated by Dehram Bora. This office was used as training camp for the congress volunteers of Gohpur.¹¹

The men and women of Kalabari and Kalangpur also undertook the work of organizing and training the people of their locality with much enthusiasm. The women were requested to take training in the Congress camps. Jonaki Gogoi of Dubia was among the trained women volunteers.¹² While the people were making their preparation for launching the movement, Pushpalata Das came to Chaiduar on 18 September 1942. The objective of her arrival was to make an agenda for the plans and programmes of 20 September to hoist the national flag at Gahpur Police Station. A large meeting was held at the Jarani Satra of Barangabari near Gahpur. Jogesh Mishra, a freedom fighter of Bihar, accompanied Pushpalata. In that meeting she made a very inspiring speech and requested the people to join the procession to Gohpur Thana.¹³

When the meeting was over, a girl with one of her friends approached Pushpalata and requested her to enlist in *Mrityu Bahini* and allow her to lead the procession. The name of this girl was Kanaklata Barua. She was very much impressed by the speech of Pushpalata in the meeting. Initially

Pushpalata and other leaders opposed to enlist the name of Kanaklata on the plea that she looked like a girl of 13 or 14 years old. She also insisted thus: “Baideo, I am not afraid of the bullets of the police, I will die to uphold the honour of the flag. Please allow me to lead the procession at Gohpur, yourself leading at Dhekiajuli; I will not allow the flag to be disgraced.” These heroic words of Kanaklata revealed her patriotism and chivalry, which was enough to contend the leaders who attended the meeting at Barangabari. She was entrusted with the leadership of *Mriyu Bahini* and Pushpalata decided to lead the women at Dhekiajuli.¹⁴

From the night of that day the Congress workers started their preparation for the programme of 20 September. The villagers were alerted to keep them ready. The trained volunteers of Kalyanpur Congress Camp were entrusted with their respective responsibilities. The people of Hawajan, Kalabari, Dubia etc made large scale preparation to hoist the flag on 20 september at Gahpur police station.¹⁵

THE HISTORIC MACH TO GOHPUR POLICE STATION:

On 20 September, preparation was made by the people of Chaiduar to take procession to Gohpur police station to hoist the national flag to defy the British rule. At Barangabari, the male volunteers were led by a local youth Mukunda Kakti and the females by Kanaklata Baruah. At about 7 o'clock in the morning the people assembled at Barangabari from where the procession was to be started.¹⁶ Kanaklata took the national flag in her hands. Few of the women who stood behind her were Someswari Bora, Debalata Barua, Bhugila Bora, Punyaprabha Barua and Maichena Barua. Thousands of men and women joined the procession. The women moved ahead of all the processionists towards the Gohpur *Thana*, situated at a distance of 7 miles from Barangabari. When the procession was on the way to Gohpur, people from villages like Baliyan, Magani, Brahmajan, Rangalial etc also came out to the street to join the crowd which increased numerical strength of the procession. All the people shouted slogans like ‘Down with British Imperialism’, ‘Swaraj is our Birth Right’, ‘Mahatma Gandhi Ki Jai’ etc. There were the singing of Jyotiprasad’s patriotic songs and instrument like drums, flutes, conch shells and brass bells were played all along the way to Gohpur.

The procession was halted at Purup Bari, a mile away from Gohpur, to ascertain the mental strength of the girl volunteers. They were warned of the possible danger and were asked to go behind or leave the procession voluntarily. But there was no sign of fear on the face of Kanaklata. Instead she vehemently opposed the instruction and said, “We the girls must not be dismissed so lightly. We are not tamed. History is replete with heroic acts of women. Does anyone expect us to live the rule the country when our valiant young men have laid down their lives? Such an idea is repugnant. They (menfolk) have immense work to do for our dear motherland. We will not allow them to die alone. We will do or die together.”¹⁷ This was the remark of Kanaklata. Thus she insisted on to continue the leadership even though knew that death was waiting for her arrival. She did not budge an inch from

her decision. Her boldness and determination also cleared the doubt of the leaders on women. The women did neither fell back nor they left the procession. Instead they continued their movement ahead of other processionists as before.

Gohpur Police Station is about a furlong off from the main road and a tank intervened between the two. By the east and west sides of the tank two lanes lead to the Thana. The eastern gate of the Thana was specially blocked on that day. The western gate was only the way through which people could enter the police station.¹⁸ This gate was guarded by Rebat Mohan Shome, the Officer-in-Charge (O.C.) of the Gohpur Thana alongwith his force consisting of 6 armed and 4 unarmed constables. Tapeswar Ojha, Sahabuddin Ahmed and Bagaram Kachari, Golok Singh were a few among those constables.¹⁹

The processionists who came from Barangabari arrived at Gohpur at about 11 A.M. This group had the strength of about 3 to 4 thousand men and women. Another group consisting of about 5 thousand people came from Kalabari side. Both the processionists met near the thana.²⁰

Some of the women that were present at that moment were Hemawati Bora, Muhila Dey, Tajabala Dihingia, Binduprabha Bora, Phuleswari Barman, Kerkeri Gam etc. They increased the women power in the procession. Some other women, still not well known to the people, also joined the procession. They are Soneswari Borua, Chandraprabha Hazarika, Padmeswari Hazarika, Buddheswari Saikia, Jyotimai Rajkhowa, Golaplata Das²¹, Bilati Bhuyan, Kusum Barthakur²² and others.

POLICE FIRING AT GOHPUR:

The procession from the west tried to enter the *Thana* by the western gate, and the procession of the east tried to enter by the eastern gate, but in vain, as the gate was closed. Both the processions contained large number of women who were at the forefront. In the western gate Kanaklata and some 10 girls were at the head of the procession. She had in her hands the national flag. For more than half an hour the people requested the O.C. to let them go in and hoist the national flag peacefully. But the O.C. would not give in. Kanaklata said, "At least you allow us the women folk to go in. We will not create any trouble. We will simply hoist the flag and come out." To this O.C said, "If you advance one step more, we will fire".²³ This threat could not deviate the people from their objective and Kanaklata said again, "You can slay our body, not our soul. If you yet persist on preventing us we must proceed, come what may". Kanaklata reminded the police officer that they were the servants of the people and the Thana belonged to the people. She said, "Unless the *Thana* officer and his men wanted to act as the servants of the people, they must clear out and allow the people to take possession of the place." Seeing no effect of appeals on the police officer, she said for the last time, "Brother, then you do your duty and let me do mine. One day the nation will say who is right and who is wrong."²⁴

When Kanaklata and other processionists failed to enter the gate by peaceful means, they became angry. There was pushing from the backside of the crowd. Now the crowd got into a harrow spot and to turn back from the

spot was not possible. Therefore some processionist who stood in the forefront had to move forward and hit the O.C. with the result that his cap fell down and stick was lost. To control the situation the O.C. ordered to fire. On receiving the order, constable Bogaram Kachari allowed two shots to go out of his rifle. The first shot pierced through the heart of Kanaklata and hit on the shoulder of Hemkanta Baruah. The second shot hit the forehead of Mukunda Kakati, another member of *Mrityu Bahini*, Kanaklata died after some time. Mukunda Kakati lost his life on the way to hospital. Khageswar Barua and Bhola Bardoloi were also severely injured by the police firing. Two fragments of a bullet also hit the forehead of Thuleswar Rajkhowa and it began to bleed. Frightened with danger, her mother Damayanti Rajkhowa embraced him and began to cry. She was also standing in the row of women processionists. However one Rampati Rajkhowa succeeded in hoisting the flag on the building of the *Thana* by the help of a ladder.²⁵

Jonaki Gogoi of Dubia was wounded while the police hit her on the chest with gun.²⁶ Lakheswari Mahanta had to remain underground for a few days. She was ordered to arrest by the police. Of course this was exempted as some policemen showed sympathetic attitude to her.²⁷

CONCLUSION:

It is rightly observed that the Indian National Congress provided a platform for the people of Chaiduar to fight against the British colonial exploitation. The Congress along with its leaders was instrumental in organizing and mobilizing the people of Chaiduar. But outside the periphery of the Congress or except the Congress elites, there were some other sections of people who came under the colonial exploitation and forced them to stand on the opposite side of the British. For example, the peasants of Kalangpur *mouza* were exploited economically and faced misbehavior by its Mouzadar Navaranga Kediya and his staff. The Mouzadar was known to be cruel among the local people and made atrocities on the peasant while collecting taxes. Such measures created resentment among the people of that locality who since long past adopted agriculture as their livelihood.²⁸ Moreover, there is evidence of collecting land revenue from the local tribes- i.e. the Mising inhabitants of Chaiduar. In all the *mouzas* of Chaiduar, some *khels* were organized among the Mising tribal community and collection of their land revenue was conducted by the Chiefs known as *Gam*. These people were also greatly affected by the British land revenue policy which hampered their traditional livelihood of agriculture. Numalia Gam, Chandrakamal Pegu, Totiram Doley, Kabigam Doley from Lohitmukh area of Chaiduar are some prominent persons from the Mising community who participated in protest movement against the British. Later on they became Congress volunteers.²⁹ Moreover, according to local sources, the protest movement in Chaiduar was also aggravated by the labourers from tea gardens like Bholaguri, etc. established during the colonial period. Unfortunately we don't have such archival record. The spontaneous participation of these sections of people played a vital role in the movement against the British exploitation to overthrow their rule in India.

FOOTNOTES:

1. *Gohpur Smritigrantha*, published on the occasion of the inauguration of Gohpur Sub-Division, Gohpur, 2000, p. 11.
2. *Anuranan: Smritigrantha*, Golden Jubilee Celebration, Gohpur High School, Gohpur, 2003, p. 18.
3. *Mukti Sangramat Chaiduarar Abadan*, A collection of biographical anecdotes of the freedom fighters, Barangabari, Sonitpur, 1974, p. (0.3)
4. Dilip Kumar Borua, *Luit Parar Birangana Kanaklata*, Golaghat, 1993, p. 6.
5. Jogendra Kalita, *Bharatar Swadhinata Sangramar Senani Swahid Mukunda Kakati*, Guwahati, 2001, p. 13.
6. *Setu*, A souvenir of Bhawana Mohotsav, Gohpur, 2008, p.54 *Gohpur Smritigrantha*, published on the occasion of the inauguration of Gohpur Sub-Division, Gohpur, 2000, p. 15.
7. K.N. Dutt, *Landmarks of the Freedom Struggle in Assam*, Guwati, 1969, pp. 94-97.
8. *Ibid.*, p. 98.
9. Punya Dhar Gogoi, *Life and Achievement of Omio Kr. Das*, unpublished, D.U. Library, pp. 150, 151, 155.
10. Achyutananda Deva Goswami, *Chaiduarat Swadhinata Sangramar Itibritta*, Gohpur, 2007, p.17.
11. *Anuranan: Smritigrantha*, Golden Jubilee Celebration, Gohpur High School, Gohpur, 2003, p.35.
12. *Mukti Sangramat Chaiduarar Abadan*, A Collection of biographical anecdotes of the freedom fighters, Barangabari, Sonitpur, 1974, p. 29.
13. Jogendra Kalita, *Bharatar Swadhinata Sangramar Senani Swahid Mukunda Kakati*, Ghy, 2001, pp. 25,26.
14. Pratima Barua and Jiban Madhuri Neog Bora (eds), *Padmabhushan Pushpalatar Chintar Rengani*, Ghy, 1999, pp.195, 201.
15. Achyutananda Deva Goswami, *Chaiduarat Swadhinata Sangramar Itibritta*, Gohpur, 2007, p. 16
16. Dilip Kumar Borua, *Luit Parar Birangana Kanaklata*, Golaghat, 1993, p. 17
17. Dipti Sharma, *Assamese Women in the Freedom Struggle*, Ghy, 1993, pp.235, 236.
18. *Report on the Atrocities Committee in 1942*, PHA File No. 76/14/1942 (Assam State Archive), p. 66.
19. Personal letter by Rebat Mohan Shome to the Magistrate of Tezpur Court, dated 21-9-42, PHA, File No.315 /1943 (Assam State Archive).
20. *Report on the Atrocities Committee in 1942*, PHA File No. p. 67.
21. Achyutananda Deva Goswami, *Chaiduarat Swadhinata Sangramar Itibritta*, Gohpur, 2007, pp. 19-23.
22. Itihase Guraka Ghaiduar, Sarbananda Bora, 2001, pp. 134- 137.
23. *Report on the Atrocities Committee in 1942*, PHA File No. 76/14/1942 (Assam State Archive), p. 67.
24. Dipti Sharma, *Assamese Women in the Freedom Struggle*, Ghy, 1993, p. 237.
25. Thuleswar Rajkhowa, *Atma Katha*, Ghy., 2005, p. 47-48.
26. *Mukti Sangramat Chaiduarar Abadan*, A Collection of biographical anecdotes of the freedom fighters, Barangabari, Sonitpur, 1974, p. 29.

27. *Anuranan*: Smritigrantha, Golden Jubilee Celebration, Gohpur High School, Gohpur, 2003, p. 37.
28. Sarbananda Borah, *Itihase Garaka Chaiduar*, Kamdewal, 2001, p. 152.
29. *Ibid.*, p. 134.

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